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CHALLENGES OF LIBERATING EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article presents concepts about “ challenges of liberating education ”. it was based on the following authors : Brandão (2005), Dussel (2000), Herkenhoff , Monteiro (2001), Santana (2009) and Freire (1996). The studies carried out make us reflect mainly on Freire's proposals , which show us the break from an elitist and banking education to a new education and a new formation of the educator , these must be committed I'm the social transformation of the human being . Liberating education aims I'm free the student , awakening them to a formal relationship of knowledge in lived experiences , reaching a level of consciousness capable of leading them I'm act within reality, in order I'm transform it into the formations of knowledge . There is , therefore , a link between learning and teaching . “ Whoever teaches learns by teaching and whoever learns teaches by learning ” (FREIRE, 1996, p.25). With these words from Freire, we educators have I'm transform the lives of those who are part of ours , that is , education will achieve the expected results if there is commitment and solidarity from both those who Teach and those who learn .

Keywords : Education. Challenges. Studies.

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the means through which human beings go from their upbringing in a family environment to entering a school, walking through a continuous process of teaching and learning. This learning formally contributes so that they can develop their skills and knowledge competencies that are presented within them or even in their experiences, leading them to critically face their development of knowledge for social transformation.

The educational process must be attractive and transformative in the eyes of those who teach and those who learn. The barriers that exist in the educational environment lead us to become discouraged at not having achieved “today” the change that we so much want from our students, but the fight must be constant in the face of this vocation that so encourages us to think about tomorrow, where we can be more through of love and dedication in the act of educating.

We know that there are still many fellow teachers who simply leave us discouraged because they do not want to reflect on the beneficial changes that can move the educational process forward.

Changes happen from the moment that human beings accept this change, as we are driven by interests that demonstrate our decisions. Educators must be aware of the four pillars of education that say we must learn to know, learn to do, learn to live with others and learn to be.

Therefore, the educator makes a difference from the moment he is concerned about his commitment to educating with solidarity, humility, love and patience to those who see in education the possible transformations provided by knowledge.

1. What is liberating education?

Education in current times shows us that we must be educators with more actions conducive to the service of quality education.

Brandão (2005, p. 107) exemplifies:

In the name of a liberating education, the exact opposite of “banking”, is that Paulo and those who seek to be his recreators assume the commitment of life and work in the service of the people of Brazil, educating and training them so that they learn to be creators of your free lives, your emancipated cultures and your just and happy societies .

We know that education aims to free the student, awakening them to a formal relationship of knowledge in lived experiences, reaching a level of consciousness capable of leading them to act within reality, in order to transform it into the formations of knowledge.

The pedagogical process involves the human being, who is the agent of his own liberation. Liberating Pedagogy uses “generative themes”, that is, students become literate with the words they use on a daily basis, always associating the literacy process with life (DUSSEL, 2000).

We must value the existing knowledge of our apprentices, as they possess knowledge that we reflect on in the classroom. Many see education as life-changing. This change is a continuous process in the life of a human being. Liberating pedagogy makes us reflect on making a difference in this process of constant struggle to aim for quality education.

Santana (2010) explains what Freire’s methodology is

In Freire’s methodology, the master positions himself alongside his apprentices so that together they can organize the activities carried out in the classes, all based on the debate on sociopolitical themes, inherent to the context they experience. Thus, his method does not only operate in the educational circuit, but also in the

economy, politics and other spheres of life in society.

In liberating education, Freire's methodology is based on sociopolitical themes, to involve his learners in the activities carried out in the classes. Today there are cross-cutting themes constituted by the National Curricular Parameters that comprise six areas: ethics (mutual respect , justice, dialogue and solidarity), sexual orientation, environment, etc. These already exist in Freire's methodology.

Cross-cutting themes permeate all areas of knowledge. They express basic concepts and values for building life in society. We are aware that transversal themes are themes that involve learning about reality. Students have knowledge regarding transversal themes that need to construct meanings and give meaning to what they learn in a formal way, that is, the school is responsible for facilitating and integrating teaching and learning actions in a contextualized way.

Liberating education sees the student as a subject of History. He sees a horizontal relationship in "educator-educator-educator" communication. Dialogue is an essential feature of liberating education. Every awareness effort is based on dialogue, exchange, discussions (HERKENHOFF, 2011).

We can say that we are responsible for our own history, because we are history makers. Dialogue is a tool for the success of a liberating education in which the educator and student learn together, based on exchanges in the face of discussions vehemently developed in pedagogical practices for better understanding and mastery of the subject discussed so that education truly constitutes the means of social transformation. Herkenhoff (2011) tells us that "humility is an ethical prerequisite of the educator who proposes to help in the process of liberation through education".

To be recognized by ourselves as educators, we

must allow good feelings to blossom for what we choose or experience, especially with regard to our students.

In the educational area, as in others, it is therefore fundamental to learn to "read" the emotions of the people in our environment, and for this there is nothing better than putting ourselves in the other person's shoes, trying to understand what the someone else is feeling it, so we can better understand their attitudes. From this understanding, the teacher is able to help his student to become aware of his emotions. Only with awareness can one unite reason and emotion. (MONTEIRO, 2001).

We obtain feelings that are shown in a positive or negative way, depending on the moments experienced by the educator and student. These are feelings driven by awareness of results, despite there being people who don't think before acting and are driven by the moment.

Monteiro (2001) tells us that there are negative emotions, which are basically three: "anger, fear and sadness. Within a classroom, it is not difficult to find these feelings in students, just as in a group of teachers it is not difficult to perceive such emotions". If we don't control ourselves emotionally, we can be responsible for even embarrassing situations.

Feelings need to be recognized and controlled by the individual, to avoid major problems in human relationships, as in classrooms, for example, unwanted behaviors such as indiscipline, mockery, side conversations, lack of interest in the content being worked on are seen. .

Just as the student needs to learn to be happy and discover the pleasure of learning, the teacher has the same needs. You need to be happy to infect your students with your happiness.

You also need to find pleasure in learning. After all, the educator is an eternal learner. And finding pleasure in teaching, he will recognize his error and the error of his student as part of the teaching-learning process. You will also have the courage to open yourself to the challenges of an education that is opposed to the traditional one, welcoming innovative projects with optimism and even innovating your pedagogical practice, from the moment you face fear not as an obstacle, but as a regulator of your actions, recognizing consciously address its limitations without stagnating in the face of initiatives (MONTEIRO, 2001) .

There are many negative and positive points in the life of an education professional. The struggle is constant, but if we are on the path we have chosen, we shouldn't always be exhausting ourselves talking about this or that. An educator means being more than just a not very fruitful day in the classroom; it is to be more for the courage to face the constant challenges on the path to be taken every day while living in this life. Being an educator with positive feelings means having love; love transformed into patience, solidarity and humility. These are beautiful feelings for anyone who considers themselves an educator.

2. The challenges of liberating education

As an educator we know that at all times in our schools we have challenges to be overcome. These overcomings will happen from the moment we as educators allow ourselves to change in our teaching and learning.

He passed his education with optimism. He believes in social changes, believes in education and believes in the training of educators. An educator, based on dialogue and love, because educating is an act of courage, of commitment to men, to liberation, to the love that was

forbidden, to dialogue and humility (FREIRE, 1997, p. 83) .

The educator and student must have this feeling of optimism in everything so that there is effect and meaning in what they do. Believing in changes is believing that you are capable of carrying out your action, aware that you can do anything if you have the will to do it. Dialogue must be privileged in education. Education does not exist for the sake of existing; education is a change in the lives of those who believe in it.

Critical Pedagogy starts from the reality of students and takes their problems and needs as a starting point. Critical educators emphasize "that any true pedagogical practice requires a commitment to social transformation, in solidarity with subordinate and marginalized groups. This necessarily conveys a preferential option for the poor and for the elimination of conditions that generate human suffering." (MCLAREN: 1997: 194)

Libertarian pedagogy brings a space of formal education, thus respecting the student's knowledge, and assumes that work is done so that students are able to start from their own language, grasp the discourse legitimized by the dominant culture; the opposite is to reinforce submission and the aspects that contribute to the reproduction of inequalities. The educator admits that he does not know everything, but he acquired knowledge through his daily life in the classroom, always encouraging the student to have freedom with responsibility; its authority does not stifle the student's freedom; his attitude is one of humility and expresses the effort to accept students as active agents, whose cultural capital and subjectivity need to be respected.

Freire's reflections on what determined the "culture of silence", characteristic of the immense majority of illiterate peasants settled in the poorest areas of Brazil, contributed to developing a philosophy and a method for finding meaning, nature, purposes and

identities among the oppressed. It is simply the vital and always necessary unity for liberation, an important part of his dialogical theory of action (RUBIO apud FREIRE1972b)

In this concept of liberation, there is nothing like Paulo Freire to speak about his conceptions about liberating education, the educator together with the student donate themselves when the business is to deposit knowledge, however dialogue prevails, the exchange of information, producing knowledge together where they establish dialogic-dialectic relationships. , thus illiterate peasants have their own identity, thus freeing them from this “culture of silence”.

According to Freire, when he states that “the oppressed as objects, as “almost things”, have no purpose. Theirs are the purposes that the oppressors prescribe to them” (FREIRE, 1987, p. 47).

The oppressed, the objectified subjects scream for their place in the world, for their condition of human dignity, they scream. And when he states that “only the power that arises from the weakness of the oppressed will be strong enough to liberate both “oppressors and oppressed”, Freire even refers to the power of shouting to make oneself heard. (FREIRE, 1987, p. 31).

The best way to teach is to seriously and passionately defend a position, encouraging and respecting, at the same time, the right to opposing speech. This will teach us the duty to fight for our ideas and, at the same time, mutual respect. Being free is the right of every human being, living in freedom, shouting and knowing how to listen to the world where each person lives in the way they want.

Defining or explaining what it means to “be a teacher”, from this perspective, becomes complex, almost impossible. For many students, teaching is just about teaching content and demonstrating commitment. This is not everything for those who like teaching.

This is how Alves expresses himself, when he says:

Educators, where will you be? In what graves did they hide? There are thousands of teachers. But a teacher is a profession, it is not something that is defined from within, out of love. Educator, on the contrary, is not a profession; it is a vocation. And every vocation is born from a great love, from a great hope (ALVES, 2000, p.16). (PELLEGGRI “APUD” ALVES).

The educator’s mission is to teach students the duty of being a competent professional. An educator allows himself to be guided by the inner strength that is sustained by his own daily experience. In this sense, he has to awaken in his mission as an educator his dimension of “loving”, of desire to teach and learn, passion for the mission of educating and transmitting knowledge, forming new generations with new values, building with the students the richness of life human experience and the experience already built by them.

A Passion that expresses itself in various ways and materializes in its enchantment with life, with freedom, with the pleasure of learning, with discovery, the practice of thinking. Being an educator actually means transmitting hope, signaling the construction of a democratic society, in which there are working, health, education and dignified living conditions for everyone.

Gadoti (1996, p.564), tells us that: “loving is an art, which requires learning, maturity, humility, courage, faith, reason, discipline, interest and concern for others. It requires solidarity.”

From this perspective, we must reflect on whether we are being a good educator or whether we do it out of obligation? We must “love” education and having due reason, courage and interest in it, the teacher must show the student how to wake up and do it. live the experience of love for education. The teacher is the one who goes to school and leaves school and returns to school always repeating the same speech to the same listeners. It’s the comedian who always presents

the same comedy to the same audience, on the same stage. When there are no more comedians and comedies on the stage, the audience screams with joy and runs away.

The example of this pedagogy is the educator Paulo Freire, who, in defending this theory, was called a clandestine and subversive, and exiled during the dictatorship. In the light of his writings, *Educação Libertadora* sees man as an unfinished being, who relates to reality and becomes a subject who knows and interferes in it. In this sense, the school can act in the formation of critical consciousness and in overcoming the dominant classes. Its role is centered on formal action, concretely questioning the reality of student's relationships with nature, and with other men, aiming at the transformation criticism of society (FREIRE, 1997, pp. 89-90).

The students' life practice. The teacher as transmitter of knowledge disappears to give way to the figure of the mediator. Although we have already said it, we reinforce our interpretation of what being an educator means by remembering that such totality makes it impossible for more than one being to be present within the school environment.

The educator passed education with optimism. Believe in changes social, invests in education and believes in the training of educators. An educator, based on dialogue and love, because educating is an act of courage, of commitment to men, to liberation, with the love that was forbidden, with dialogue and humility (FREIRE 1997, p. 83).

The educator needs to have confidence and make the student believe in their ability to fulfill their vocation natural of being more . The being educated reflects an image of the educator as his hero where the subject is to transmit knowledge, with this the image of the knowledgeable subject is created, always betting on social changes he finds himself forced to create the new horizon of the being an educator. The knowledge that makes

citizenship possible is not structured within the circuits of formal social organization, which is why it is created by circuits of invention.

CONCLUSION

We conclude that the challenges of education exist to be overcome and this overcoming is faced with our actions that make education the bridge between wanting to always seek more to successively innovate our continuous training process and our pedagogical practices.

We always set out for new challenges, towards construction through knowledge , the teacher then becomes a mediator between the student and knowledge, which is why he needs to be well informed, motivated and willing to carry out construction work, that is, social transformation . Because the "need" is something that is either satisfied (if it is an inner requirement) or, if it is not, it does not allow the individual to subsist as such. Popular education is a committed and participatory education guided by the perspective of realizing all the rights of the people.

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